

Methodology for developing professional deontological competence of students

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Abstract. The article provides information on the implementation of a number of important and urgent tasks facing the higher pedagogical education system, such as improving the quality and efficiency of education, ensuring its openness, humanism and individual orientation, ensuring continuity between all levels of education, integration with the world or educational environment, and developing professional deontological competence in students.

Keywords: professional development, deontological competence, education, science, information technologies, pedagogical deontology, competence, competence, science, methodological approaches, junior high school teacher, professional ethics,

Introduction. The development of social life poses a number of extremely important and urgent tasks for the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Some of these include radically improving the quality of education, solving the problems of interdisciplinarity and coherence between disciplines, subjects, and educational stages, ensuring the openness of education to all, and accelerating the processes of integration with the developed scientific and educational environment of the world. Despite the rapid penetration of information and innovative

technologies into the content of all spheres of human life, the widespread discussion of the issue of computerization of the educational process, the introduction of information technologies into it, the scale of practical work carried out in this area in higher educational institutions and the attention paid to it cannot be called at the required level. The analysis of the results of scientific research and our observations made it possible to determine that the use of information technologies in the educational process of higher education is superior to traditional methods, and little attention is paid to the use of computers and innovative didactic technologies in the direct educational process [1].

Literature analysis . Our country has set a number of important urgent tasks for the higher pedagogical education system, such as improving the quality and efficiency of education, ensuring its openness, humanism and individual orientation, ensuring continuity between all levels of education, and integration with the world educational environment. In the 21st century, which is considered the century of information technologies, it is necessary to create the necessary conditions for the formation of the younger generation as individuals who can enrich science and production with their knowledge, intellectual and creative capabilities with new methods and technologies. Pedagogical training of future primary school teachers depends, first of all, on the high-quality training of pedagogical personnel in higher educational institutions. The level of competence of specialists, professional skills, professional deontological competence, and the ability to correctly and purposefully manage pedagogical processes determine the success of shaping the personality of the student. This poses an urgent task for the higher pedagogical education system, as well as all organizations responsible for education and personnel training in general, to further study the issues of professional preparation of future teachers for organizing and managing the processes of educating a well-rounded personality.

Discussion . Uzbekistan has all the necessary conditions for the transition to the modern model of innovative development. This model is based on the wide and effective use of the created scientific and technical potential, the widespread implementation of the achievements of fundamental and applied sciences, technologies requiring deep knowledge, and an increase in the number of highly qualified, talented personnel. This serves as a necessary condition and a solid foundation for our country to join the ranks of the world's economically and industrially developed countries. Today's high level of development of science, technology, engineering, and production automatically puts new social requirements on the agenda. Among these social requirements, society, and, in particular, the force that drives the development of industries on its basis - the training of qualified personnel, and the improvement of the system aimed at this goal, are of decisive importance. The need for training qualified personnel arose at the very beginning of the development of the industrial sector, when production enterprises appeared, but it still retains its relevance. The main reasons for this are the emergence of new directions and specialties in connection with the social, economic and cultural development of society, the need to train personnel in them, the formation of the need for consistent improvement of professional knowledge, skills and abilities of specialists in a changing, fast-paced era, as well as the increased demand for specialists to withstand strong competition in the labor market. In the current conditions, a well-founded system of continuing education, in particular the stage of higher education institutions, plays a special role in providing qualified personnel for the social, economic and cultural sectors. As mentioned above, the rapidly developing era sets the task for specialists to be ready for rapid changes, keep pace with the times, develop self-formation from a social and professional perspective, and develop professional deontological competencies. In order for specialists to fully meet this requirement, it is very important to organize the educational process in

higher educational institutions. The qualifications of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions, that is, the full preparation of future specialists for professional activity, their pedagogical skills, personal qualities that ensure the priority of humanistic ideas in the educational process, and the ability to objectively monitor and evaluate students' knowledge must correspond to existing social requirements. It also requires them to study advanced pedagogical practices, use modern pedagogical and information technologies, develop their skills and qualifications, and continuously develop their professional deontological competence.

Result. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, effective work is being carried out to improve the level of professional deontological training of students of higher pedagogical educational institutions, to increase their knowledge, skills and qualifications in modern pedagogical and related fields. In developing curricula, special attention is paid to the formation of students' professional deontological competence and creative abilities. In addition, the experience of such developed countries as Germany, Japan, South Korea, and Singapore is widely used in the preparation of curricula. At this point, it is worth noting that we need to identify the following areas for further improving the professional training of students of higher educational institutions of education: in order to achieve a continuous increase in the level of professional deontological training of graduates of higher educational institutions, their study of the latest achievements in the field of theory, scientific and practical research, technological progress and innovations in the professional disciplines being taught, as well as modern methods of organizing the educational process; continuous improvement of qualification requirements, curricula, programs and methods for all specialties based on their direct practical application in the educational process, having thoroughly studied the latest achievements of modern

pedagogical, innovative and information and communication technologies; increasing the level of mastery of foreign languages of students of higher educational institutions and effectively using it in constantly improving their professional and scientific activities; training qualified teachers by conducting continuous professional practice at a high level in educational areas of higher educational institutions and achieving full-fledged completion of graduation qualification works in selected facilities; improving the work carried out during their scientific internships in order to more effectively organize the scientific activities of master's students. In particular, teaching them to analyze domestic and foreign scientific literature, scientifically substantiate the results obtained from experimental and test work carried out on scientific research; organizing business trips of personnel to developed foreign countries in order to further improve the training of qualified teachers and scientific pedagogical personnel. The provision of all these areas will serve to further increase the responsibility of students and future teachers of higher educational institutions for organizing their pedagogical activities and professional self-development.

The words competence and competence are related and complementary concepts. Therefore, the competence system combines a number of competencies and competences in terms of practical and theoretical training. After all, specialists whose competence is not sufficiently developed and developed cannot perform their duties perfectly. Competent is a professional who has knowledge in a specific field and has acquired competencies specific to this field. The differences in the concepts of “competence” and “competence” in terms of practical and theoretical training in the system are manifested in the following:

- competence is a predetermined social

requirement in state standards, which is an educational (professional) preparation that is important for each professional to effectively work in a specific field. • competence is the knowledge, skills, qualifications, personal and professional qualities acquired by the professional in his specialty, and is the experience gained in a specific field. The final result is the training of highly qualified personnel and increasing their potential.

CONCLUSION In conclusion, the systematic organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions of pedagogy plays an important role in increasing the professional deontological competence of future primary education teachers, in training highly qualified personnel who are able to withstand strong competition in the labor market. This, in turn, guarantees the high-quality organization of the educational and upbringing process in higher educational institutions, and in achieving high efficiency in training qualified personnel.

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